

ANALYSIS OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL IMAGE OF CHILD CHARACTERS IN THE DRAMAS OF MCDONAGH

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Abstract. The dramaturgy and plays of Martin McDonagh (McDonagh, Martin 1970) are considered a part of national Irish literature because the author himself is Irish. At the same time, the playwright's contribution to the development of English drama and English theater cannot be denied. McDonagh's plays are staged in many London theaters, are actively discussed by theater critics on the pages of English daily newspapers, and the author's plays are deeply studied by English literary critics. McDonagh's works continue and develop the trends of English drama, so in the 1990s and 2000s, the playwright works on the aesthetics of the theater of cruelty, for which the theme of children's problems, relationships with parents and the world of childhood is relevant (The Cripple of Inishmaan, 1996 and The Pillow man, 2003).

Key words. Children's Character, Emotions, Crossover Fiction, dramaturgy, storytelling, negative, positive, neutral expression.

Introduction. "The Cripple of Inishmaan" is one of the brilliant works of the playwright that shows the Irish character, the events of the work take place on the edge of Ireland, on one of the small islands. On an island imagined to be forgotten by God, the characters constantly repeat to each other the same stories, known to all the inhabitants of the island, in different variations, and the veracity of these stories arouses doubt in both listeners and readers.

In fact, this drama is a different version of the Irish provincial story "The Man from Aran" (1934), directed by RJ Flaherty half a century ago. P. Lonergan, a well-known researcher of M. McDonagh's work, writes in his monograph: The Cripple of Inishmaan is one of McDonagh's most unexpected dramas. The main motive in the work is the story of the death of the parents of the main character of the play - Billy, a disabled teenager who was orphaned at an early age. All the characters of the play tell this story in different ways.

Analysis. In McDonagh's play, the theme of the hero's attempts to find his childhood history and finally move away from his birthplace is combined. It is noteworthy that Billy dreamed of going to America to become a star, just like his character, traveling to America was a childhood and teenage dream for

McDonagh. In addition, the famous playwright, who had the opportunity to travel once in the United States, did not hide his childhood admiration for America and the idea of filming what was happening. McDonagh says in one of his interviews: "To me, as a child, as a beggar, as a child of the working class, to visit America seemed an impossible dream. Every time I went to America it always felt like I was in a movie or a dream like a 70s movie. But for the hero, saying goodbye to Ireland turned out to be as impossible as finding the unsolved secrets of his childhood, the lack of answers to the question of the fate of his family forces Billy, like other characters in the play, to weave stories about his parents strengthens the painful connection with the homeland, dead parents and unhappy childhood:

"B i l l y." A home barren, aye, but proud and generous with it, yet turned me back on ye I did, to end up alone and dying in a one-dollar rooming-house, without a mother to wipe the cold sweat off me, nor a father to curse God o'er the death of me, nor a colleen fair to weep tears o'er the still body of me. A body still, aye, but a body noble and unbowed with it.

An Irishman! (Pause.)

The problems of authenticity and fiction, the narrator's responsibility for the authenticity of his story, and issues related to family relationships are also considered by M. McDonagh in the play "The Pillow man" (2003). In the work, the author chooses a boring police station in an unknown town as a place, without showing national colors or ethnic stereotypes.

Theater critics and literary critics criticized the playwright for the shallow content of the work, but the structural features of the dramatic work were neglected by researchers, in fact, it is a complex work in terms of the composition of the play and the interdependence of several story levels.

The text of the drama maintains a balance between two seemingly contradictory and mutually exclusive genres - the epic and the dramatic. The dramatic scene (the police questioning Katurian about the children's deaths, staging Katurian's stories about their murders) serves as a frame for a series of stories about the suffering and death of the children.

The heroes of Katurian's story "The Writer and the Writer's Brother" are Katurian himself and his brother Michal. The story follows the suffering of Katurian's older brother Michal, who was tortured by his parents for years. The situation and gestures before Katurian's narration and stories, and then the staging of the event, which creates the effect of a multi-dimensional, multi-level stage space, interrupting the narrative process, occurs as follows:

"Katurian, sitting on a bed among toys, paints, pens, paper, in an approximation of a child's room, next door to which there is another identical room, perhaps made of glass, but padlocked and totally dark. Katurian narrates the short story which he and the mother, in diamonds, and Father, in a goatee and glasses, enact".

Discussion. The British literary critic R.R. Russell says that the characters and events in McDonagh's dramas in general are intertextual: "The feature of McDonagh's works is that they are copied from television series, westerns, detective dramas and fairy tales." For example, the image of police officers and interrogation scenes are taken from F. Kafka's "The Court" and O. Mirbo's "Garden of Torture", the conventions of time and space resemble the chronotype of absurd dramas, the stories created by Katurian are folk tales and legends. , in addition, the playwright openly refers to the plot of the legend of the Pied Piper of Hamelin, and the stories of children's suffering have features of fable-telling and Gothic literature.

All three of McDonagh's dramas feature child characters, and there are similarities between them: for example, Billy was born mentally retarded to a disabled, pregnant mother who was beaten by her father, and she spent her entire childhood in captivity and endured abuse from her parents. There is another feature that unites the characters of McDonagh's dramas: both Michal and Billy have hobbies or regular activities: Billy can stare aimlessly at cows for hours, while Michal can listen to his brother's horror stories for a long time with fear and pain. . The tendency of the characters to constantly repeat the same actions creates a dull and monotonous life for them. Hobbies also help the characters mask and fill their inner voids, which McDonagh describes as typical of every child character: "the character's hobby, pastime, boringly emphasized feature is also the playwright's is a writing method as well as a characterization tool. For some heroes, a hobby is a matter of pride, for others it is a way to get rid of boredom.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it is worth noting that a typological analysis of McDonagh's characters reveals that both Billy and Michal have characteristics of several types of children, although Michal, despite his age, plays the role of the "victim", "simulator" child. plays There are child-victim-type traits common to these characters.

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